

A Study of the Experience of Able Mathematicians in Secondary Schools in Ireland

Judi Mills

Maynooth University

In 1993, the Report of the Special Education Review Committee in Ireland outlined best practise for students who were 'exceptionally able and talented' in a number of areas including 'specific academic aptitude' and 'creative productive thinking'. However, to date, there has been limited research focus on how to challenge able mathematicians. In 2010, the Project Maths curriculum reform was introduced into Irish schools at both Junior and Senior cycle levels. There is much emphasis in the new syllabus on teaching for conceptual understanding, reasoning, justification and problem solving (NCCA, 2015) which is in line with the recommendations above. My study aims to examine whether able mathematicians feel challenged in post-primary schools in Ireland and what can be done, within a diverse classroom, to give them a more engaging learning experience. As part of the project, I designed a series of workshops through which I could examine the attitudes of students to creative problem solving. This paper is primarily a review of international research into the importance of creative tasks for identifying and challenging able mathematicians and a description of the design of my study. Data is still being collected but a preliminary analysis has been carried out, the findings of which will be discussed.

Introduction

My research project aims to examine how challenged second level mathematics students feel, what they enjoy about their mathematics classes and which aspects they believe will help them reach their mathematical potential. In this paper I will describe the design of my project and give some preliminary results based on data gathered from 95 students in 5 different Irish schools. I have designed and trialled workshops to push the students into areas of uncertainty and encourage them to question, explore and discuss mathematics. In Barbeau & Taylor (2009) mathematical challenge is seen as an essential aspect of education in that it provides students with opportunities to experience enjoyment and satisfaction whilst also enhancing valuable life skills such as patience, persistence and flexibility. Providing students with an engaging experience that enhances their understanding of the mathematics of real life is a key feature in the current Irish syllabus (NCCA, 2015). However, early research into the impact of Project Maths showed that students are still “being presented with tasks that do not require them to engage widely with the mathematical processes promoted through the revised syllabuses”, (Jeffes, Jones, Wilson, Lamont, Straw, Wheeler, & Dawson, 2013, p. 45). There is evidence that the level of cognitive demand in Leaving Certificate examinations has increased since the introduction of the Project Maths syllabus (O'Connor, Ní Shúilleabháin, & Meehan, 2019) but the extent to which the aims and objectives of the syllabus are being implemented in the classroom needs further investigation. Textbooks still play a key role in classroom instruction (Jeffes et al., 2013) yet research has shown that those used in Ireland offer a low level of high cognitive demand or creative thinking tasks (O'Sullivan, 2017). In light of this my study will examine whether able mathematicians, who may have an excellent

capacity for creative reasoning and transfer of conceptual knowledge, are given sufficient opportunities to do so in the classroom.

Defining an Able Mathematician

An able mathematician is seen in this study as a student who has the potential to achieve highly in school and thereafter. In light of research which has shown that a lack of high achievement in school mathematics assessments does not prevent mathematical accomplishment (Pehkonen, 1997), an able mathematician also includes those who have a great interest in mathematics yet may not be high achievers in exams. To allow all students to have the opportunity to maximize their creativity, standard assessments of their ability should not be the only determining factor for their selection as an able mathematician. Intelligence, personality and perseverance need consideration as well, given the evidence that there are many high achievers who do not excel in traditional assessments (Mellroth, 2018; Nolte & Pamerien, 2017; Sheffield, 2003).

Literature Review

Why Able Mathematicians Need Challenge

The literature on education for mathematically able students stresses the need for challenge (Mann, 2006; Nolte & Pamerien, 2017; Sheffield, 2003) but defining exactly what we mean by challenge is more complex. The Cambridge online dictionary describes challenge as being faced with ‘something that needs great mental or physical effort in order to be done successfully and therefore tests a person’s ability’. By such a definition all students deserve to be challenged, the difficulty comes with knowing how to challenge all students and balancing this with other priorities as a teacher. Nolte & Pamperien (2017) believe that challenging problems are essential for the development of cognitive and emotional skills in high ability students. Similarly, Sheffield (2003) suggests that challenge is instrumental in the development of the brain and that mathematics is the ideal discipline in which to do this. Creativity is identified as one of the key characteristics of mathematically able students (Leikin & Lev, 2013) and as such should be an essential element of classroom instruction.

The Role of Creativity in Recognising and Fostering Challenge

The last two decades have seen an increased interest in mathematical research on giftedness and creativity and, in particular, in the crucial role creativity has on mathematical cognition. This heightened interest can be seen by the introduction of thematic groups on giftedness and creativity in international conferences such as the International Congress on Mathematics Education (ICME) and The International Group for Mathematical Creativity and Giftedness (MCG). Research papers for these conferences have focused on the importance of creativity and on specific areas such as defining, recognising and fostering creativity.

Defining creativity has proved a complex task and there is a lack of a widely accepted definition amongst researchers. Up until recently it was felt that this “lack of an accepted definition for mathematical creativity hindered research efforts” (Mann, 2006). Torrance, the acclaimed “Father of Creativity”, based his assessment of creativity on a measure of the

evidence of fluency, flexibility, novelty and elaboration in a mathematician's work (Leikin & Lev, 2013). Building on Torrance's concepts, multi-solution tasks have been shown to be a means by which the 'relative creativity' of students can be identified and fostered (Leikin & Lev, 2013). The definition that best describes my study is that creativity at school level is "the process that results in unusual (novel) and/or insightful solution(s) to a given problem" that are new relative to the student's mathematical experiences and those of his peers (Liljedahl & Sriraman, 2006, p.19).

Inhibiting Factors to Pursuing Creative Tasks in Schools

One of the major obstacles in regular classrooms is the 'myth' that high ability students can teach themselves (Sheffield, 2017). Research in Finland and Britain on the role teachers can have has shown that in some cases up to 40% of high ability students are underestimated by their teachers (Freeman, 1998). Other surveys quote teachers have felt "hindered by constraints on time and material resources in teaching bright pupils, and that any available extra provision was targeted towards the least able" (Freeman, 1998, p.11). A teacher's ability to see the creative potential of students can also be obscured by an over emphasis on classroom instruction based on teacher examples and rote learning of algorithms. This is substantiated by research on the theory of functional asymmetry in the human brain which has highlighted the danger of placing too much focus on routine algorithms, which exercise the left hemisphere, at the expense of the creativity and spatial awareness, which exercise the right (Pehkonen, 1997). However, there has been a move towards support for Pehkonen's theory and more recently it has been acknowledged that mathematical creativity can, and must, be developed in all students (Mellroth, 2018; Sheffield, 2003).

The Irish Context

Ireland has catered for 'gifted' students through summer schools and extra-curricular courses such as the Olympiad, Maths Circles and Irish Centre for Talented Youths (CTYI) since the 1990's. My study sees creativity as a characteristic of a wider section of students than those who have been classified as 'gifted' and aims to investigate opportunities to expand creative reasoning skills within the school curriculum.

The motivation behind the Project Maths curriculum reform, in 2010, was largely to address the findings in reports on international assessments such as The Programme for International Assessment (PISA) and Trends in International Mathematics and Science study (TIMSS). In 2015, Ireland was found to be below the OECD average in the higher order level 5/6 problem solving tests in PISA (OECD, 2016). As a country, Ireland performs well on 'knowing' procedures but higher order thinking and 'reasoning' have been neglected in favour of drilling students on procedural fluency. In order to enhance the recognition of the need to foster creative reasoning, both teachers and students must believe in its merits.

Theoretical Framework

My research is guided by Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development and Sriraman's Five Principles to Maximize Creativity (Figure 1). These frameworks form

the structure upon which the study was designed. By doing so I hope to investigate how challenged able mathematicians feel in Irish classrooms and what impact creating an environment based on Sriraman’s five principles can have on their motivation, enjoyment and perseverance when solving unfamiliar tasks.

Vygotsky’s Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development

A fundamental construct of Vygotsky’s theory is his belief that creativity is the key to cognitive development by enabling students to construct their own knowledge through collaboration with others. He suggested that “development processes do not coincide with learning processes. Rather, the development process lags behind the learning process” (Vygotsky, 1978, p.90). For this reason, student learning should be in what he called ‘zones of proximal development’ (ZPD) where students work on more advanced tasks than those they currently feel comfortable with. Collaboration and exposure to tasks in the ZPD are considered critical in enabling students to reach their mathematical potential.

Sriraman’s Five Principles to Maximize Creativity

More recently, Sriraman (2005) outlined five principles to maximize creativity for second level students (Figure 1). The first of these requires students to be given the opportunity to engage in the four-stage creativity process of the Gestalt psychology principle: initiation-incubation-illumination-verification. Of these four stages, the most important stage with regard to creativity is the incubation stage when the mind unconsciously reaches a solution. Sriraman also emphasised the appreciation of unusual student solutions, exposing students to uncertainty and creating an environment that encourages student discussion.

Figure 1

Harmonizing creativity and giftedness at upper second level.

Note. This is reproduced from Sriraman (2005).

Methodology

I designed 2 workshops to allow students to work in small groups on multi-solution tasks. The workshops were held a week apart to enable the students to incubate the problems posed and some of the techniques that had worked for them. Before the workshops, the

students were given a Likert scale survey to gather data on their current experience of mathematics in school and their level of self-confidence with regards to mathematics. After participating in the workshops, the students were re-surveyed to assess the impact, if any, of the workshops on their thinking, problem-solving strategies, self-efficacy and motivation. Voluntary focus group interviews, of 3 or 4 students, approximately 40 minutes long, were held a week after the workshops to give the students an opportunity to answer more open-ended questions and to discuss in more detail their experience of the tasks in the workshops.

Structure of workshops

The workshops were run face to face, in three different schools in early 2020, but the pandemic necessitated that those for the final two schools were run via an online platform using a similar group set-up via breakout rooms. The schools selected included single sex and mixed gender schools from a variety of locations. The students were selected from Transition Year and the teachers were asked to offer the workshops to students who were either high achievers in school, or those who showed a particular interest in mathematics but may not have been in the top 15% in traditional assessments. They were then placed into randomly selected groups of three or four where they were given one or two tasks per workshop that were designed to be unfamiliar and suitable for diverse classrooms. I was guided by the definition of ‘an unfamiliar task’ as “one for which students have no algorithm, well-rehearsed procedure or previously demonstrated process to follow”, (Breen & O’ Shea, 2015).

Other key features, based on my chosen frameworks of Vygotsky (1986) and Sriraman (2005), were that the tasks selected were challenging, multi-solution tasks intended to encourage creative thinking, peer collaboration and perseverance whilst avoiding putting the students under time pressure to solve them. The students were given no guidance as to the method to employ and were required to make connections across various strands of the Leaving Certificate syllabus to solve the tasks. They were encouraged to discuss the problem-solving strategies they employed as a group and the merits of a number of different solution methods presented to the class. My role was that of a facilitator where I only intervened to ask probing questions or to encourage a line of thinking that the students had suggested but lacked the confidence to pursue.

Sample Tasks

The Nrich Steel Cables task (see Figure 2 below) is an example of one of tasks selected because of its suitability to challenge all students simultaneously in diverse classrooms. The students were given the template on the left, a ‘size 5’ cable with 61 strands, and asked to find how many strands would be in a ‘size 10’ cable in as many ways as possible. They were then asked to find how many strands would be in a ‘size n ’ cable and to explain their reasoning to the group. The next phase of the task was carried out in the second workshop to give students time to incubate the problem. The brief was to discuss the solutions presented to them (diagram on the right of Figure 2 below) and to suggest how the methods employed could be used to find the strands in a ‘size 10’ and ‘size n ’ cable.

Figure 2

Steel Cables Task.

Note. Reproduced from www.nrich.maths.org/7760

Data Collected

In addition to the student surveys, the discussions in the working groups and breakout rooms were audio recorded and the written workings of the students were collected as data. I have so far conducted nine focus group interviews based on questions aimed at assessing the students’ experience of school mathematics and the workshops. Of the 95 students who have agreed to participate I have collected surveys from 80 students and 26 have taken part in the group interviews. I have one remaining set of workshops and interviews to complete.

Preliminary Results

A preliminary analysis of the responses to both surveys has been carried out and the percentages of responses to a sample of questions in the surveys are given in the table below:

Table 1

Sample of results from 80 student surveys.

Survey Question	Strongly agree /Agree %
I am often bored in class while the teacher explains the solution to other students.	71.1%
Most of the time we work on mathematics problems from the textbook.	86.8%
Most problems I do in school can be answered by recall of examples and formulae.	93.4%
Having to think about the method in the workshops was different to what usually happens when we use the textbook in class.	91.4%

I have only carried out a preliminary analysis of the focus group interviews for 3 schools but can give a flavour of their answers to questions about their school experience and their impressions of the workshops. Some recurring themes have emerged from the interviews analysed, such as student descriptions of class as “very repetitive”, “a lot of waiting around”, “we don’t ever discuss maths” and “we just stick with the method we are shown in the example, we don’t have to think about it”. Discussion and peer collaboration, as advocated by Vygotsky and Sriraman, do not seem to be key features of mathematics class for these

students. Similarly, there is little evidence to support the integration of Sriraman's 'five principles to maximize creativity' in their normal classrooms. In addition to the above recurrent themes, key words that have been reiterated in these particular interviews were feelings of "boredom" in school classes in contrast to feelings of "freedom" in the workshops.

Discussion

The preliminary analysis highlights that able mathematicians feel that classroom instruction is overly focused on examples rather than concepts. In contrast, the main aspects of the workshops they enjoyed were having to use trial and error to think of methods for themselves and discussing these with their peers. This study is grounded in the belief that creativity is an essential aspect of providing challenge to able mathematicians but as evidence suggests (Mellroth, 2018; Nolte & Pamerien, 2017 and Sheffield, 2003) it can also be accomplished in a diverse classroom, such as is common in Ireland. The anticipated dilemma for teachers is how to ensure that the students are challenged without being overwhelmed by the cognitive leap from the traditional algorithmic textbook questions. It is hoped that the combination of data in this study will help facilitate the exploration of creative problem-solving methodologies for diverse classrooms in Ireland.

References

- Barbeau, E., & Taylor, P. (Eds.). (2009). *ICMI Study—16 Volume: Mathematical challenge in and beyond the classroom*. Kluwer.
- Breen, S., & O'Shea, A. (2015). Adams, G. (Ed.) *Proceedings of the British Society into Learning Mathematics* 35(1) February.
- Report of the Special Education Review Committee (SERC) (1993). Retrieved January 12, 2021 from https://www.sess.ie/sites/default/files/Categories/Exceptionally_Able/SERC_Exceptionally_Able_Talented.pdf
- Freeman, J. (1998). *Educating the very able: Current international research*. The Stationary Office.
- Jeffes, J., Jones, E., Wilson, M., Lamont, E., Straw., Wheater, R., & Dawson, A. (2013). *Research into the impact of Project Maths on student achievement, learning and motivation: Final report*. NFER.
- Leikin, R., & Lev, M. (2013). Mathematical creativity in generally gifted and mathematical excelling adolescents: What makes the difference? *ZDM – The International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 45(2), 183–197.
- Liljedahl, P., & Sriraman, B. (2006). Musings on mathematical creativity. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 26, 17-19.
- Mann, E. (2006). Creativity: the essence of mathematics. *Journal for the educated of the gifted*, 30(2), 236-260.
- Mellroth, E. (2018). *Harnessing teachers' perspectives: Recognizing mathematically highly able pupils and orchestrating teaching for them in a diverse ability classroom*. Karlstad University Press.

- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA). (2015). Leaving certificate mathematics syllabus: Foundation, ordinary and higher level. Stationary Office.
- Nolte, M., & Pamperien, K. (2017). Challenging problems in a regular classroom setting and in a special foster programme. *ZDM – The International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 49(1), 121-136.
- O’ Connor, R., Ní Shúilleabháin, A. & Meehan, M. (2019). Investigating cognitive demand of higher-level leaving certificate mathematics examination tasks pre- and post-curricular reform. In L. Harbison and A. Twohill (Eds.), *Proceedings of the seventh conference on research in mathematics education in Ireland*, (pp. 203-210). MEI.
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2016). *Pisa 2015: Results in focus*. Paris.
- O’ Sullivan, B. (2017). *An analysis of mathematical tasks used at second-level in Ireland*. PhD thesis. DCU, Ireland.
- Pehkonen, E. (1997). The state-of-art in mathematical creativity. *ZDM – The International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 29(3), 63-67.
- Sheffield, L. (2003). *Extending the challenge in mathematics. Developing mathematical promise in K-8 students*. Corwin Press.
- Sheffield, L.J. (2017). Dangerous myths about “gifted” mathematics students. *ZDM – The International Journal on Mathematics Education*, 49(1), 13-23.
- Sriraman, B. (2005). Are mathematical giftedness and mathematical creativity synonyms? A theoretical analysis of constructs. *Journal of Secondary Gifted Education*, 17(1), 20-36.
- Vygotsky, L.S. (1978). *Mind in society. The development of higher psychological processes*. Cambridge.